

How effective are audiobooks in values education? Sample of TRT Children's Library*

Özge Karakaş Yıldırım, Afyon Kocatepe University, Faculty of Education, Department of Turkish Education

Abstract

Values are crucial in guiding people's behavior as they fulfill their duties and responsibilities within their society. Values are instilled in children from an early age, both in families and through education. Education plays a significant role in passing values from one generation to the next. In the process of teaching values, both families and teachers introduce children to different materials. Books are often a preferred material for conveying values. Each book has something valuable to teach children, whether it is printed, electronic, or in other formats. Audiobooks have become a popular option, especially for children who are still learning to read and write. The audiobooks used during the pre-reading phase, play a crucial role in teaching values to children. This study is a qualitative case study that aims to examine and identify the values present in the audiobooks available in the TRT Children's Library application. The analysis will be conducted within the context of the Türkiye Century Education Model. The findings revealed that the values presented in the examined audiobooks were not evenly distributed. The themes of friendship, responsibility, and diligence were prominently discussed, while values such as justice, aesthetics, and freedom were rarely mentioned.

Keywords: virtue-value-action, values education, Türkiye Century Education Model, audiobook, TRT Children's Library

1. Introduction

Various social forms have developed from the past to the present. Every society differs in culture, life, ideals, and beliefs. However, one commonality remains: Every society needs order to ensure its continuity. This order arises from the principles, judgments, and rules that have developed through the interactions of society's members. Rules, principles, and judgments that guide an individual's social relationships and determine their behavior are shaped within the framework of specific standards. These standards shape individual and societal behavior, determining what is valued and preferred in society, and together they constitute values (Akbaş, 2008; Korkmaz, 2020: 39). The values embraced by the majority of society such as love, respect, justice, and friendship, are essential characteristics that an ideal person should embody. These values contribute to creating a livable society, ensuring peace and order within the community (Akay, 2018; Aykaç, 2023; Kuşdil & Kağıtçıbaşı, 2000; Shrestha & Gupta, 2019; Topal, 2019; Yalar & Yanpar Yelken, 2011). While definitions of value vary, there is a lasting belief that a particular course of action is preferable either personally or socially (Rokeach, 1973). From an empirical perspective, value represents an individual's attitude towards an object, event, or phenomenon, and its significance in relation to another object, event, or phenomenon (Apressyan, 2022; Schwartz & Bilsky, 1987). The value assigned to an object, event, behavior, or phenomenon can vary and change over time, as it is shaped by individual and societal needs. At the same time, this value often reflects a standard that is generally accepted by society (Kolaç, 2021; Korkmaz, 2020). Values are connected to the desired states or behaviors, guiding individuals toward positive actions. For instance, while 'honesty' is considered a value, 'dishonesty' reflects the absence of this value and is not regarded as a value itself (Aydın, 2011). From birth, individuals encounter the unwritten rules, norms, and values of their society, learning to navigate these social elements (Bolat, 2016; Kolaç, 2021). An individual's ability to lead a peaceful and happy life within their society relies on the effective functioning of social structures. In turn, the efficacy of these social structures is dependent on the alignment of the values held by individuals with those structures (Kuşdil & Kağıtçıbaşı, 2000).

Throughout history, one of humanity's most significant endeavors has been to nurture individuals who demonstrate desired behaviors (Korkmaz, 2020; Köylü, 2020). As long as people live in society, a

* A part of this study was presented as a paper at the IV. International Congress of Educational Research and Teacher Education, held from December 21 to 23, 2023.

major concern for the future will continue to be the upbringing of individuals. The reason for this concern is that the continuity and peace of a society rely on its members being moral. Individuals are expected to develop personal value systems that align with the community's shared values and to exhibit behaviors consistent with societal beliefs and norms. Each society imparts its beliefs, cultural aspects, and values to individuals through various educational practices. Value education is the process through which an individual learns to adapt to society. This adaptation starts within the family, where parents implicitly or explicitly pass on their personal values to their children and continues systematically in educational institutions. It is further influenced by the media, peers, and the surrounding environment (Akay, 2018; Akbaş, 2008; Halstead & Taylor, 2000; Kolaç, 2021; Sun, 2025). The primary responsibility of education is to cultivate individuals who not only acquire academic knowledge, skills, and behaviors but also embrace fundamental values (Balci, 2021: 42; Eken & Öksüz, 2019; Gouda & D'Mello, 2019).

Values education, which is organized within educational institutions, is also highlighted in the curricula. Values education was formally introduced as a separate section in the Turkish Curriculum published in 2017. This section outlines ten fundamental values: justice, friendship, honesty, self-control, patience, respect, love, responsibility, patriotism, and helpfulness (MoNE, 2017; MoNE, 2019). Education aims to provide students with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, behaviors, and habits necessary to become responsible individuals and engaged citizens. Consequently, it is a profession shaped by values (MoNE, 2017). Values education, has been restructured in the 2024 Türkiye Century Education Model to focus on the concept of virtue-value-action. This new model highlights fundamental values such as justice, respect, and responsibility. These three fundamental values are closely interconnected with other values such as justice, family integrity, diligence, friendship, sensitivity, honesty, aesthetics, privacy, mercy, modesty, freedom, patience, healthy living, respect, love, responsibility, thrift, hygiene, patriotism, and helpfulness. In addition to teachers, who are the most critical element in providing value education in schools, books and texts also play a significant role in conveying values (Kumbasar, 2011; Topal, 2019). Literary texts serve as practical tools for transferring values. Books and texts, whether read or listened to, play a crucial role in transmitting values (Balci, 2021; Kolaç, 2021; Lovat & Clement, 2008). In Turkish lessons, values education is effectively achieved through texts. These texts not only prepare children for life but also contribute significantly to their personality development during preschool and primary school, which is the most crucial period for values education (Kolaç, 2021).

In the digital age, the methods and materials used for creating and accessing texts have changed significantly, largely due to advancements in multimedia technology. This has enabled people to access information in various formats (Kim, 2021). While traditionally a book is defined as a work printed on sheets of paper and bound together with hard covers, this definition is no longer adequate in today's context (Baskin & Harris, 1995). In recent years, there has been a noticeable shift towards the preference for electronic and audiobook formats, alongside traditional printed books. Audiobooks are appealing to people of all ages, particularly preschool children who have not yet developed reading skills, as well as visually impaired individuals and those with learning difficulties, such as dyslexia. Listening materials are often included in school curricula to help students develop their listening skills. Many researchers agree that all texts, whether for listening or reading, play a crucial role in the transfer of values (Akay, 2018; Balci, 2021; Kaya & Taşkın, 2020; Kolaç, 2021; Kumbasar, 2011; Topal, 2019). An audiobook is a book that is listened to rather than read in the traditional way (Have & Pedersen, 2021). Audiobooks are primarily created from printed or e-published books, featuring a narrative structure and read by either a single reader or multiple readers (Best, 2020). Audiobooks, often referred to as "talking books" or "phonographic books," originated in the 1870s when Thomas Edison recorded stories on gramophones. This innovation aimed to enhance the storytelling experience that was already a cherished part of home life (Cahill & Moore, 2017; Rubery, 2011; Rubery, 2016; Venkatesh et al., 2015). Shortly after its invention, the phonograph was used for literary purposes, and the first recordings of full-length novels were made in Britain and the United States during the 1930s. The demand for recorded literature emerged in both countries due to soldiers returning from World War I with eye injuries and other

individuals with visual impairments who were unable to read Braille (Rubery, 2011). However, the technology for audiobooks dates back much further than recording human voices on specific formats such as CDs, cassettes, gramophones, and MP3 files. Literary works originally emerged as oral traditions. The history of recorded books dates back to ancient times, when stories, commentaries, poems, and histories were shared by storytellers. During this period, literature was experienced through listening rather than reading (Baskin & Harris, 1995). Although the history of audiobooks dates back to ancient times, the option to listen to books on audio tapes became widely available after World War II. The term “audiobook” first emerged in connection with audio cassettes.

In the 1980s, digital compact discs became increasingly popular, and from 2002 to the present, audiobooks have been available for download and streaming on the Internet through compressed digital formats such as MP3 (Have & Pedersen, 2016; Rubery, 2011). Audio storytelling is an age-old tradition that has evolved from war tales narrated by artists in Ancient Greece to the immersive experience of listening to stories through headphones in the 21st century (Karakas-Yıldırım, 2023). Audiobooks provide an accessible option for individuals who struggle with reading printed books for various reasons. They also offer a flexible listening experience, allowing users to enjoy books while engaging in activities such as walking, cycling, exercising, or driving (Baskin & Harris, 1995; Have & Pedersen, 2021). A study on the benefits of audiobooks for different age groups revealed that for children starting school (ages 4-7), listening skills develop before reading skills, and their exposure to various speech patterns enhances verbal fluency. In the same study, independent readers aged eight to 12 reported that audiobooks allowed them more time to read due to increasing homework and exam pressures (Alcantud-Diaz & Gregori-Signes, 2014). Audiobooks not only support the principles of lifelong learning in the educational process but also serve as valuable resources for teachers. They enhance the teaching process and play a significant role in instilling values that are often highlighted in educational curricula. Through audiobooks, students can practice reading independently, access a wide range of books, experience diverse lives and behaviors, and learn socially accepted behaviors through these experiences (Alcantud-Diaz & Gregori-Signes, 2014). Audiobook culture has become an important part of education and literature, leading to the rise of many audiobook apps. There are many applications (Storytel, TRT Dinle, Kitapyurdu Sesli Kitap, Seskit) and websites (724dinle.com, akev.edu.tr, kitup.net, seslikutuphane.ibb.gov.tr, seskitaparsivi.com) that are utilized in education and preferred by individuals for their reading habits. There are also apps specifically designed for children. The TRT Children’s Library app offers books in both audio and electronic formats for children. This study aims to classify audiobooks in the application based on 20 values related to virtue, value, and action, as outlined in the Türkiye Century Maarif Model 2024 Secondary School Turkish Course Curriculum.

2. Method

This study is designed to examine the values presented in the audiobooks available in the TRT Children’s Library application, which is one of the audiobook platforms. It operates within the framework of virtue, value, and action as outlined in the Türkiye Century Maarif Model 2024 Secondary School Turkish Course Curriculum. This research employs a case study approach, a qualitative research method aimed at discovering and understanding the meanings that individuals or groups attach to a specific social or human issue (Creswell, 2014: 4).

2.1. Study Material

The study material includes 280 books organized into five themes: From Within Life, Curious Scientist, Our Fairy Tales, Nature’s Tale, and Our Heroes, in the TRT Children’s Library. In 2025, these

books are accessed from the application, and 121 texts from the themes “From Within Life” and “Our Heroes” were included in the study. Texts can be accessed through both listening and reading. 121 audiobooks from the TRT Children’s Library were analyzed through content analysis. The books are categorized by themes, and frequency values were recorded.

Table 1. Quantitative distribution of books used in the research according to themes and age level in TRT Children’s Library application

	Audiobook Themes					TOTAL	%
	From Life	Curious Scientist	Our Fairy Tales	Nature’s Tale	Our Heros		
Books for ages three and older	9	9	8	15	5	46	16,4
Books for ages four and older	22	17	8	10	9	66	23,5
Books for ages five and older	13	10	12	21	10	66	23,5
Books for ages six and older	11	6	7	9	10	43	15,3
Books for ages seven and older	13	9	8	8	19	57	20,3
Books for ages eight and older	-	-	-	2	-	2	0,71
Total Number of Books	68	51	43	65	53	280	100

Table 1 illustrates the distribution of book numbers by age level within the themes presented in the TRT Children’s Library. The application features books organized into five themes: “From Within Life”, “Curious Scientist”, “Our Tales”, “Nature Tales”, and “Our Heroes”, for children aged three-eight. When examining the distribution of books by theme, there is a total of 68 books in the category “From Within Life.” The “Curious Scientist” theme includes a total of 51 books. The “Our Fairy Tales” theme contains a total of 43 books. The “Nature Tales” theme features a total of 65 books. “Our Heroes” theme includes a total of 53 books. The application contains various books categorized by age suitability based on the following ratios to the total number of books: The ratio of books suitable for ages three and above to the total number of books in the application is 16% (f=46), the ratio of books ideal for ages four and above is 23% (f=66), the ratio of books suitable for ages five and above is 23% (f=66), the ratio of books ideal for ages six and above is 15% (f=43), the ratio of books suitable for ages seven and above is 20% (f=57). The ratio of books suitable for ages eight and above to the total number of books is 1% (f=2). The greatest number of books is found in the four and five age groups (f=66), while the least is in the eight age group (f=2). When examining the distribution of books by theme, it is noteworthy that the largest number of books falls under the theme “From Within Life” (f=68), while the smallest number is found in the theme “Our Tales” (f=43). A total of 121 books were analyzed, encompassing the themes “From Within Life” and “Our Heroes.”

2.2. Data Collection and Analysis

In case studies, data collection techniques like interviews, focus groups, and document analysis are utilized (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). The data for this study were collected through document analysis. This method can be used either on its own or in combination with other data collection methods (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013: 217). Data was collected using the TRT Children’s Library app, which

provides audiobooks for children and is easily accessible for every child and family, without requiring membership or fees. 121 audiobooks from the TRT Children’s Library were analyzed within the context of 20 values outlined in the 2024 Türkiye Century Education Model's virtue-value-action framework. These audiobooks were categorized based on the actions associated with these values and underwent content analysis to determine their frequency values.

3. Results

This study examined audiobooks in the TRT Children’s Library application within the Türkiye Century Education Model's virtue-value-action framework. In this section, values were categorized based on the themes addressed in the TRT Children’s Library application and the books suitable for various age groups.

Table 2. Distribution of audiobooks on the theme “From Within Life” in the TRT Children’s Library application according to age and values within the virtue-value-action framework.

From Within Life						
	Age					
Value	3+	4+	5+	6+	7+	f
V1. Justice	That is My Train				Fikri and Fahri See Me	2
V2. Family Integrity	Monster’s Heart, Cute Monster Becomes a Big Brother	Pudino Plays With his Sister,	Loving the Little Ones,	Dino and Pino		5
V3. Diligence	Dinosaur	Atakan Goes Fishing with His Father	Farmer Mumu, Author Nana, Teacher Vudi,		Meryem Leads	6
V4. Friendship	Efe and Ece at the Guesthouse, Efe and Ece at the Picnic,	A Nice Summer Vacation, Sunny Days, Let’s Create Love, Cemile is Going to the Park	Welcome Oya, Seeing Love, Could You Please Be Kind?	Super Goal Keeper, Most Beautiful Is Your Sweet Word, First Day at School, Schoolbag at the Vacation	If You Meet You Will Love, Meryem is Being Friendly, Fikri and Fahri Move Aside	16
V5. Sensitivity	-	Tolga and Duman, Super Agent	Welcome Oya		Fahri and Fikri My Tender-hearted Friend	4

V6.Honesty	-			My Mother Became a Dedective	Fikri and Fahri Red Presidential Armband	2
V7. Aesthetic	-		Cook Hamham			1
V8. Privacy	-	At Park			If You Allow	2
V9. Mercy	-		Author Nana	The Cat of the Bosphorus Titiz,	Fahri and Fikri My Tender- hearted Friend	3
V10. Modesty	-	Cemile's Birthday	Teacher Vudi, Police Sampi, Yağız's Birthday	My Mother Became a Dedective, Super Goal Keeper	If You Allow	7
V11. Liberation	Efe and Ece Occupations, Dream Planet	Cemile Rides a Pony, Cemile Goes to the Park		Our Neighbour Auntie Macide		5
V12. Patience	-	Atakan Goes Fishing With His Father		Holiday Candies	Fahri and Fikri Everything Has Its Time, Meryem Is Respected	4
V13. Healthy Living	-	Summer, At the Doctor's, Pudino Plays With His Sister, Rabbit the Bıdıbık at the Dentist, How Will Mutlu Recover?	First Aid	Holiday Candies	Meryem Self- control, Fikri and Fahri My Dear Father	9
V14. Respect	-	Blue Gaki, Rabbit the Bıdıbık Apologizes, Super Agent	Could You Please be Kind?, Please Listen to Me	Our Neighbour Auntie Macide	If You Meet You Will Love, Meryem Is Respected, Fikri and Fahri My Dear Father	9

V15. Love	Efe and Ece at the Guesthouse	-	Welcome Oya, Seeing Love	The Most Beautiful is Your Sweet Word	Meryem is Being Friendly	5
V16. Responsibility	-	Tolga and Duman, At the Doctor's, Pudino Helps His Father, Pudino is at the Fruit Festival, Pudino Loves Sharing, Rabbit the Bıdıbık is in the Forest, Rabbit the Bıdıbık at the Dentist	First Aid, Grocer Tosun, Cook Hamham, Police Sampi	Little Locomotive, Time Travel, First Day at the School	Meryem Self-control	14
V17. Thrift	-	-			Fahri and Fikri My Tender-hearted Friend	1
V18. Hygiene	I am Getting My Hair Cut	At the Park, At the Doctor's	Cook Hamham		Meryem Self-control	4
V19. Patriotism	-	-				-
V20. Benevolence	-	Tolga and Duman, Pudino Helps His Father	Grocer Tosun, Police Sampi	Our Neighbour Auntie Macide	Meryem Is Respected, Elif and Ahmet Benevolence	7

Table 2 presents the distribution of audiobooks on the theme “From Within Life”, categorized by age and values. A total of nine books aimed at ages three and above were examined under the theme “From Within Life.” The following values were identified in the audiobooks analyzed: liberation (f=2), friendship (f=2), family integrity (f=2), love (f=1), diligence (f=1), justice (f=1), and hygiene (f=1). The most commonly cited aspect of liberation is the emphasis on being courageous and enterprising. The focus is on prioritizing family unity within the value of family integrity. In the value of friendship, the books “Efe and Ece at the Picnic” and “Efe and Ece at the Guesthouse” emphasized caring for friends and spending quality time with them. A total of 22 books aimed at children aged four and older were analyzed based on a specific theme. The value that appeared most frequently in these books was responsibility (f=8). A total of 22 books aimed at children aged 4 and older were analyzed based on a specific theme. The value that appeared most frequently in these books was responsibility (f=8). Some books, such as “Pudino Helps His Father”, “Rabbit the Bıdıbık at the Dentist”, and “Pudino Plays with

His Sister” convey multiple values. The primary value highlighted in these stories is responsibility, which underscores the importance of having a sense of duty and fulfilling one’s obligations to oneself. In the value of healthy living, books like “Summer”, “Rabbit the Bıdıbık at the Dentist”, “At the Doctor”, and “How Will Mutlu Heal?” highlight the importance of caring for human health. A total of 13 books for children aged five and older were examined under the theme “From Within Life.” The value most frequently highlighted in these books was responsibility (f=4). This was followed by friendship (f=3), modesty (f=3), and diligence (f=3) – each also appearing three times. Other notable values included respect (f=2), helpfulness (f=2), sensitivity (f=1), hygiene (f=1), aesthetics (f=1), mercy (f=1), family integrity (f=1), and healthy living (f=1). Several books (Policeman Sampi, Cook Hamham, Teacher Vudi, Grocer Tosun, Welcome Oya) notably contain more than one value. The value of responsibility is characterized by completing tasks fully and promptly, as well as taking ownership of decisions made. The value of friendship highlights the importance of caring for friends, spending time with them, and supporting one another. In the books that discuss the value of diligence, such as “Teacher Vudi” and “Farmer Mumu”, determination is highlighted. 11 books for readers aged six and older were analyzed in this theme. The most frequently recurring value in these books was friendship, which appeared four times (f=4). The value of friendship is followed by the values of responsibility (f=3), modesty (f=2), honesty (f=1), patience (f=1), respect (f=1), helpfulness (f=1), love (f=1), mercy (f=1), family integrity (f=1), healthy living (f=1), and freedom (f=1). Certain books, such as “The Most Beautiful is Your Sweet Word”, “First Day at School”, and “Super Goalkeeper”, explore multiple themes. The most prominent theme is friendship, which emphasizes the importance of supporting friends during both good and bad times, as well as collaborating with them to achieve common goals. The value of responsibility highlights having a sense of duty and fulfilling one’s obligations to oneself. Books that address the value of modesty, such as “Super Goalkeeper” and “My Mom Became a Detective”, emphasize self-awareness and the importance of avoiding ostentation and bragging. 13 books aimed at readers aged seven and above were analyzed in relation to their underlying themes. Values most frequently represented in these books were friendship and respect, each occurring three times. These were followed by patience (f=2), responsibility (f=2), helpfulness (f=2), healthy living (f=2), privacy (f=1), modesty (f=1), sensitivity (f=1), mercy (f=1), thrift (f=1), diligence (f=1), love (f=1), hygiene (f=1), justice (f=1), and honesty (f=1). Some books, such as “Meryem Self-Control”, “If You Know Me You Will Love Me”, and “Fahri and Fikri: My Tender-Hearted Friend”, contain multiple values. In terms of the value of friendship, the emphasis is placed on actions such as enjoying time spent with friends and making an effort to understand their feelings and thoughts. For the value of respect, actions that stand out include recognizing the inherent worth of each individual and evaluating relationships based on mutual respect. Overall, the most prevalent value represented in the books is friendship (f=16), followed closely by responsibility (f=14). The following values are ranked by frequency: healthy living (f=9), respect (f=9), helpfulness (f=7), modesty (f=7), diligence (f=6), love (f=5), freedom (f=5), family integrity (f=5), hygiene (f=4), patience (f=4), sensitivity (f=4), mercy (f=3), privacy (f=2), honesty (f=2), justice (f=2), thrift (f=1), and aesthetics (f=1). It was noted that some values, such as patriotism, were not represented in any of the texts.

Table 3. Distribution of audiobooks with the theme of Our Heroes in the TRT Children’s Library application according to age and values in the virtue-value-action framework

Our Heroes						
Value	Age					
	3+	4+	5+	6+	7+	f
V1. Justice	-	-	-	-	-	0
V2. Family Integrity	-	-	-	-	The Mystery of Symmetry	1
V3. Diligence	-	Nasreddin Hodja Time Traveler - Robot Friend, Nasreddin Hodja Time Traveler - Game Over, Ege and Gaga How to Spread Seeds, Ege and Gaga Where Did the Beads Go?	Aslan- Bird Observatory, Aslan- Maze Explorers	Precious Stone, My Right My Left My Front My Back, So Many Leaves, New Moon	The Mystery of Symmetry, Rafadan Crew Science Heroes, Geometric Objects, Rafadan Crew on Detective Pursuit, Fractions Filled Our Stomachs	15
V4. Friendship	Thanks Momo		Rafadan Crew- Snow is Coming, Rafadan Crew- Unrelieved Hiccups, Aslan- Scarecrow, Rafadan Crew- Game Changer	Gaga's Stomach Hurts	Rafadan Crew- More Than a Friend, Rafadan Crew Science Heroes, Rafadan Crew- Treasure Hunt, Rafadan Crew- Unique Collection, Rafadan Crew- Adventure is on Our Trail, Rafadan Crew- Put Yourself in Her Shoes, Fractional	14

					Ice Cream Maker, Rafadan Crew Tournament	
V5. Sensitivity	-	Ege and Gaga Where is the Lost Chicken?, Ege and Gaga - Where are the Seeds?	Aslan- Empathy Room, Rafadan Crew-Water is Life, Rafadan Crew- Misunderstanding	What If Water Never Flows?, Voice in the Kitchen	Rafadan Crew- Put Yourself in Her Shoes, Uzay's Birthday Codes	9
V6.Honesty	-	-	-	-	Presidential Race	1
V7. Aesthetic	-	-	-	-	Rafadan Crew- Ventriloquist Kamil	1
V8. Privacy	-	-	-	-	Rafadan Crew on Detective Pursuit, Chasing Roman Numerals	2
V9. Mercy	-	-	-	-	-	0
V10. Modesty	-	-	-	-	Presidential Race, Geometric Objects, Rafadan Crew- Put Yourself in Her Shoes, Fractional Ice Cream Maker	4
V11.Freedom	-	-	-	-	We Measure Liquids	1
V12. Patience	Strange Flower	Ege and Gaga: Who Ate the Carrot?	-	Flown Flown Balloon Flown, Astronaut Gaga	-	5
V13. Healthy Living	Where are Momo, Şıp and Tıp?	-	-	Gaga's Stomach Hurts	Rafadan Crew- Health Guards	3

V14. Respect	-	-	-	-	Rafadan Crew- Adventure is on Our Trail, Rafadan Crew- Put Yourself in Her Shoes, Chasing Roman Numerals	3
V15. Love	-	Nasreddin Hodja Time Traveler - On the Trail	-	-	Rafadan Crew- Treasure Hunt	2
V16. Responsibility	Tako's Teeth	Nasreddin Hodja Time Traveler - Doing Farming	-	Gaga's Stomach Hurts	Rafadan Crew- Treasure Hunt, Rafadan Crew- Adventure is on Our Trail, Geometric Objects, Fractions Filled Our Stomachs, The Story of Zero	8
V17. Thrift	-	-	-	What If Water Never Flows?	-	1
V18. Hygiene	-	-	Aslan- Pencil Sharpener Piggy Bank	Astronaut Gaga	-	2
V19. Patriotism	-	-	-	-	-	0
V20. Benevolence	Lost Skateboard	-	-	Air in the Soil	Rafadan Crew- Adventure is on Our Trail, Uzay's Birthday Codes	4

Table 3 illustrates the distribution of audiobooks on the theme of “Our Heroes” in the TRT Children’s Library application, categorized by age level and values. An analysis of audiobooks for ages three and above, centered on the theme of “Our Heroes”, reveals insights based on the framework of

virtue, value, and action. Five books were examined, showcasing the following values: patience (f=1), helpfulness (f=1), healthy living (f=1), responsibility (f=1), and friendship (f=1). The focus is on being consistent in the value of patience, kind in the value of helpfulness, and caring about human health in the value of healthy living. A total of nine books for children aged four and above were examined in relation to the theme. The values included in these books were as follows: diligence (f=4), sensitivity (f=2), patience (f=1), responsibility (f=1), and love (f=1). In the most frequently repeated value, diligence involves actions that highlight the use of curiosity for scientific development and the fulfillment of responsibilities in both personal and group activities. The sensitivity value highlights the importance of valuing the environment and living beings. 10 books for children ages five and up were examined under the theme “Our Heroes.” The books explored various values, including friendship (f=4), sensitivity (f=3), diligence (f=2), and hygiene (f=1). The value of friendship is demonstrated through kindness, enjoyment of time together, and helping each other with problems. In the sensitivity value, topics such as valuing the environment, living beings, and appreciating people and society are discussed. The value of diligence emphasizes the importance of being curious, asking questions, and actively engaging in learning. A total of 10 books suitable for ages six and older were reviewed in relation to this theme. The examined books included the following values: diligence (f=4), sensitivity (f=2), patience (f=2), friendship (f=1), hygiene (f=1), thrift (f=1), helpfulness (f=1), responsibility (f=1), and healthy living (f=1). The value of diligence emphasizes the importance of accessing reliable information, and being open to diverse ideas, arguments, and new insights. In the sensitivity value, the importance of valuing the environment and living beings is emphasized, while investigative and questioning behaviors are highlighted in the diligence value. In the “Our Heroes” theme, a total of 19 books for ages seven and up were analyzed. The following values were highlighted in these books: friendship (f=8), diligence (f=5), responsibility (f=5), modesty (f=4), respect (f=3), sensitivity (f=2), helpfulness (f=2), privacy (f=2), family integrity (f=1), honesty (f=1), love (f=1), aesthetics (f=1), healthy life (f=1) and freedom (f=1). The value of friendship is the most prominent theme in the books. This is illustrated through actions such as enjoying time spent with friends, preserving national identity and culture while engaging with people from diverse backgrounds, and prioritizing quality time with friends. The significance of being investigative and questioning is highlighted through the value of diligence illustrated in five different books. The value of modesty highlights the importance of self-awareness and constructive behaviors in human relationships. The value of respect highlights the respect for the environment, national and moral values, and being polite draws attention. In the overall analysis, it is evident that the value most represented by books within this theme is diligence (f=15), closely followed by friendship (f=14). These two values are followed by sensitivity (f=9), responsibility (f=8), patience (f=5), helpfulness (f=4), modesty (f=4), healthy living (f=3), respect (f=3), love (f=2), hygiene (f=2), privacy (f=2), honesty (f=1), thrift (f=1), aesthetics (f=1), and freedom (f=1). Some values, such as patriotism, justice, family integrity, and mercy, were not represented in any of the texts. Additionally, it was noted that audiobooks for ages three and four did not include many values. In contrast, audiobooks for ages seven and older offered a more diverse range of values.

Table 4. Distribution of texts on the themes “From Within Life” and “Our Heroes” by age groups and values

Theme	From Within Life					Our Heroes				
	3+	4+	5+	6+	7+	3+	4+	5+	6+	7+
Value	Total					Total				

Justice	1	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	0
Family Integrity	2	1	1	1	-	5	-	-	-	-	1	1
Diligence	1	1	3	-	1	5	-	4	2	4	5	15
Friendship	2	4	3	4	3	16	1	-	4	1	8	14
Sensitivity	-	2	1	-	1	4	-	2	3	2	2	9
Honesty	-	-	-	1	1	2	-	-	-	-	1	1
Aesthetic	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	1
Privacy	-	1	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	-	2	2
Mercy	-	-	1	1	1	3	-	-	-	-	-	0
Modesty	-	1	1	2	1	5	-	-	-	-	4	4
Freedom	2	2	-	1	-	5	-	-	-	-	1	1
Patience	-	1	-	1	1	3	1	-	-	2	3	6
Healthy Living	-	5	1	1	2	9	1	-	-	1	1	3
Respect	-	3	2	1	3	9	-	-	-	-	3	3
Love	1	-	2	1	1	5	-	1	-	-	1	2
Responsibility	-	7	4	3	2	16	1	1	-	1	5	8
Thrift	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	1	-	1
Hygiene	1	2	1	-	1	5	-	-	1	1	-	2
Patriotism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Helpfulness	-	2	2	1	2	7	1	-	-	1	2	4

Table 4 provides a comparative breakdown of the values in audiobooks under the themes “From Within Life” and “Our Heroes” for various age groups. The most frequently occurring values in audiobooks on the theme “From Within Life” were friendship (f=16) and responsibility (f=16). Other important values included healthy living (f=9), respect (f=9), helpfulness (f=7), freedom (f=5), modesty (f=5), family integrity (f=5), diligence (f=5), love (f=5), and hygiene (f=5). In audiobooks themed “Our Heroes”, the most frequently emphasized values were diligence (f=15) and friendship (f=14), followed by sensitivity (f=9), responsibility (f=8), and patience (f=6). The analysis revealed that the value of thrift was illustrated in only one book among each theme. The value of hygiene is not addressed in any of the audiobooks recommended for ages six and up in the book “From Within Life.” Additionally, hygiene is not emphasized in any audiobooks recommended for ages three, four, and seven and up in the book “Our Heroes.” Finally, the value of patriotism was missing from all audiobooks examined within the two themes. Additionally, the values of justice and mercy were not represented in any texts within the “Our Heroes” theme. In analyzing the distribution of values in the total number of texts on both themes, it is important to note that friendship is frequently mentioned, appearing 30 times. This represents approximately 25% of the total number of texts analyzed. Out of the 121 texts examined, around 20% (24 texts) discussed the value of responsibility, while 17% (20 texts) highlighted the value of diligence. These figures suggest that the most frequently addressed values in the texts were friendship, responsibility, and diligence.

4. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

Audiobook applications have recently become popular among all age groups due to their convenience. Audiobook applications that feature texts specifically designed for children are favored by young children who have not yet learned to read, as well as by those who can read. These applications can be used alongside other activities, making them a versatile choice for both groups. Audiobooks, which attract a wide audience, play an important role in values education, particularly for children. This study examines the audiobooks available in the TRT Children’s Library application, focusing on the Türkiye Century Education Model’s virtue-value-action framework. 121 texts were analyzed under the

themes “From Within Life” and “Our Heroes”. The analysis of the values presented in the 121 books reveals some interesting patterns. Certain values, such as responsibility, diligence, and friendship, are frequently mentioned throughout the texts. In contrast, other values, including aesthetics, justice, and thrift, are rarely addressed. Additionally, there are values like patriotism that do not appear in any of the examined texts. In the study conducted by Durhat and Ökten (2020), the authors examined the texts associated with the “Virtues” theme in Turkish textbooks, focusing on fundamental values. The analysis revealed that the values of patriotism and self-control were not addressed in the “Virtues” theme at any grade level. The study found that textbook content often emphasizes values such as responsibility, diligence, and friendship. In Topal’s (2019) research on teaching ten fundamental values, teachers identified friendship and responsibility as the most commonly addressed values in their lessons. In contrast, values such as justice and honesty were noted to be covered less frequently. In a study conducted by Gündüz and Bağcı (2019) with science teachers, it was found that the most emphasized value that teachers aimed to impart to students in the unit on “Humans and the Environment” was the value of responsibility. The study by Eken and Öksüz (2019) found that the value of honesty was not included in first-grade Turkish textbooks and was given minimal attention in other grade levels. As the virtue-value-action application developed within the Türkiye Century Education Model is a new initiative, the concept of values education in the literature highlights ten fundamental values. Some values are rarely exemplified in audio, electronic, or printed texts related to values education, whether in the context of ten fundamental values or the concept of virtue-value-action. Patriotism is also one of these values. In their study examining the Fifth Grade Turkish Textbook through the lens of virtue, value, and action, Geçimli and Kayahan Yüksel (2024) noted that the value of patriotism is only addressed in the theme “Let's Get to Know Atatürk.” Numerous studies have examined the ten fundamental values, which have often been criticized for their shortcomings (Akhan et al., 2020; Topal, 2019). With the introduction of the 2024 Türkiye Century Education Model, values have been organized into 20 categories within a virtue-value-action framework. Additionally, behaviors associated with these values have been categorized under the heading of “action”. Although a more descriptive structure for values has been developed, it has been observed that these values are not treated equally in audiobook texts. Additionally, the study by Durhat and Ökten (2020) concluded that fundamental values are unevenly distributed. This study is unique because it is the first to examine audiobooks within the framework of virtue, value, and action, an area that has not been previously researched. The findings indicate that certain values are frequently highlighted in audiobooks, while others are either minimally represented or not included at all. Additionally, the distribution of values in audiobooks is not as balanced as observed in other studies.

The TRT Children’s Library application is easily accessible to everyone and serves as an alternative reading and listening material for children who can read as well as those who cannot. For those who cannot afford books, the application’s free access will positively influence the preference for audiobooks. This situation will highlight audiobooks as an alternative to printed books. While developing audiobook applications for effective value transfer, the texts within them should be considered separately regarding how they convey value. In early childhood, value education is crucial; values must be presented in a balanced manner in related texts. The texts in audiobook applications should be regularly updated to align with values education and the topics they cover.

References

- Akay, İ. (2018). The element disarraying construction in the historical children's novels of Ahmet Yılmaz Boyunağa: The Art of Metaphor. *Turkish Studies Language and Literature*, 13(28), 1-30. DOI: 10.7827/TurkishStudies.14430
- Akbaş, O. (2008). Değer eğitimi akımlarına genel bir bakış [A General overview of values education trends]. *Journal of Values Education*, 6(16), 9-27.
- Akhan, N. E., Subaşı, E., & Açıl, F. B. (2020). Öğretmen adaylarının kök değerlere ilişkin görüşleri [Prospective teachers' views on core values]. *Journal of Education and New Approaches*, 3, 115-134.
- Alcantud-Diaz, M., & Gregory- Signes, C. (2014). Audiobooks: improving fluency and instilling literary skills and education for development. *Tejuelo*, 20, 111-125.
- Apressyan, R. G. (2022). Values paradigms of character education. *Education&Pedagogy Journal*, 1(3), 5-12. DOI: 10.23951/2782-2575-2022-1-5-12
- Aydın, M. (2011). Değerler, işlevleri ve ahlak [Values, functions and morality]. *Eğitime Bakış [Perspective on Education]*, 7(19), 39-45.
- Aykaç, N. (2023). *Examining the root values within the book of the Arabian Nights and the contribution of this fairy tales to children's literature* [PhD Thesis]. Inonu University.
- Balcı, M. (2021). Değer eğitiminde hikâye türünün kullanılması [Using the story genre in values education]. In E. Kolaç (Ed.) *Metin ve etkinliklerle karakter ve değer eğitimi [Character and value education through texts and activities]* (pp 42-58). Nobel Publishing.
- Baskin, B. H., & Harris, K. (1995). Heard any good boks lately? The case for audiobooks in the secondary classroom, *Journal of Reading*, 38(5), 372-376.
- Best, E. (2020). Audiobooks and literacy: A rapid review of the literature. A National Literacy Trust Research Report. National Literacy Trust.
- Bolat, Y. (2016). Understanding the social values and values education, *The Journal of Academic Social Science*, 4(29), 322-348. DOI : 10.16992/ASOS.1283
- Cahill, M., & Moore, J. (2017). A sound history: Audiobooks are music to children's ear. *Children and Libraries*, 22-29.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. Sage Publications.
- Durhat, G., & Ökten, C. E. (2020). Relatedness of root values to the "Virtues Theme" in Turkish coursebooks. *Journal of Mother Tongue Education*, 8(3), 675-693. <https://doi.org/10.16916/aded.678498>

- Eken, N. T., & Öksüz H. İ. (2019). Investigation of the narrative texts in the Turkish textbooks (from the 1st to the 4th grades) regarding the basic values in the Turkish language teaching program. *Journal of Mother Tongue Education*, 7(2), 384-401. <https://doi.org/10.16916/aded.543009>
- Geçimli, M., & Kayahan Yüksel, D. (2024). Türkiye century education model virtue-value-action framework: A study in the context of fall term 5th grade Turkish course book. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 8, 160-174. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30830/tobider.sayi.20.9>
- Gouda, G. G., & D'Mello, L. (2019). Excellence through value education- A case study of Sharada Vidyanikethana Public School, *International Journal of Case Studies in Business*, 3(1), 10-19. DOI: 10.47992/IJCSBE.2581.6942.0031
- Gündüz, M., & Bağcı, M. (2019). The awareness about base values and teaching methods of values of Science teachers, *Journal of International Social Sciences Education*, 5(2), 184-197.
- Halstead, J. M., & Taylor, M. J. (2000) Learning and teaching about values: A review of recent research, *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 30(2), 169-202, DOI:10.1080/713657146
- Have, I., & Pedersen, S. (2016). *Digital audiobooks new media, users, and experiences*. Routledge.
- Have, I., & Pedersen, S. (2021). Reading audiobooks. In I. Elleström (Ed.). *Beyond media borders* (pp 197-216). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Karakaş Yıldırım, Ö. (2023). TRT Çocuk Kitaplık uygulaması çerçevesinde sesli kitap uygulamalarında tema [Theme in audiobook applications within the framework of TRT Children's Library application]. In E. Aydın (Ed.). *Dijital çağda çocuk edebiyatı [Children's literature in the digital age]* (pp 225-244). Nobel Publishing.
- Kaya, M., & Taşkın, O. (2020). Okulda değerler eğitimi (Values education in schools). In M. Köylü (Ed.). *Teoriden pratiğe değerler eğitimi [Values education from theory to practice]*. (pp 89-114). Nobel Publishing.
- Kim, N. (2021). E-book, audiobook or e-audiobook: The effects of multiple modalities on EFL comprehension. *English Teaching*, 76 (4), 33-52.
- Kolaç, E. (2021). Edebi metinlerle değer eğitimi [Values education through literary texts]. In E. Kolaç (Ed.) *Metin ve etkinliklerle karakter ve değer eğitimi [Character and value education through texts and activities]*.(pp 1-16). Nobel Publishing.
- Korkmaz, M. (2020). Değerler eğitimi yaklaşımları [Approaches of values education]. In M. Köylü (Ed.). *Teoriden pratiğe değerler eğitimi [Values education from theory to practice]*.(pp 37-65). Nobel Publishing.
- Köylü, M. (2020). Ahlak ve değerler eğitimine duyulan ihtiyaç [The need for moral and values education]. In M. Köylü (Ed.). *Teoriden pratiğe değerler eğitimi [Values education from theory to practice]*. (pp 3-17). Nobel Publishing.
- Kumbasar, E. (2011). *Muzaffer İzgü's novels examined for values education* [Master Thesis]. Karadeniz Technical University.

- Kuşdil, M. E., & Kağıtçıbaşı, Ç. (2000). Türk öğretmenlerin değer yönelimleri ve Schwartz değer kuramı [Value orientations of Turkish teachers and Schwartz value theory], *Turkish Journal of Psychology*, 15(45), 59-76.
- Lovat, T. J., & Clement, N. D.(2008). The pedagogical imperative of values education, *Journal of Beliefs & Values: Studies in Religion & Education*, 29:3, 273-285, DOI:10.1080/13617670802465821
- Ministry of National Education (MoNE). (2017). *Turkish Language Curriculum (Grades 1-8)*. Ministry of National Education Publishing.
- Ministry of National Education (MoNE). (2019). *Turkish Language Curriculum (Grades 1-8)*. Ministry of National Education Publishing.
- Rokeach, M. (1973). *The nature of human values*. Free Press.
- Rubery, M. (2011). Introduction. Talking books. In M. Rubery (Ed.) *Audiobooks, literature and sound studies* (pp 1-25). Routledge.
- Rubery, M. (2016). *The untold story of the talking book*. Harvard University Press.
- Schwartz, S. H., & Bilsky, W. (1987). Toward a universal psychological structure of human values. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 53(3), 550-562.
- Shrestha, B. K., & Gupta, P. (2019). Impact of value education in personal behaviour of students: A case study of Nepal. *Nepal Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 1-8. DOI: 10.3126/njmr.v2i3.26285
- Sun, L. (2025). A narrative inquiry of the intergenerational transmission of cultural family values in mainland China, *Journal of Beliefs & Values*, 46 (1), 65-81, DOI: 10.1080/13617672.2023.2241289
- Topal, Y. (2019). Values education and ten root value. *Mavi Atlas [Blue Atlas]*, 7 (1), 245-254.
- Yalar, T., & Yanpar Yelken, T. (2011). Determining the teachers opinions on improving values education and developing a programme module sample. *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*, 10 (38), 79-98.
- Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2013). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri[Qualitative research methods in social sciences]*. Pegem Akademi Publishing.
- Venkatesh, A., Lalitha, M. V., Narayana, J., & Mahesh, K. (2015, 18-20 March). *Wikiaudia: Crowdsourcing the production of audio and digital books*. Proceedings of the International MultiConference of Engineers and Computer Scientists, Hong Kong.